

**MODELS AND METHODS FOR
INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF
INNOVATIVE RESEARCH**
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USE OF MARKETING IN WHOLESALE TURNOVER PLANNING

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Abstract: *This article discusses the importance of planning wholesale turnover in the context of an innovative economy based on the principles of marketing, ways to plan wholesale turnover through the collection and analysis of primary marketing information.*

Key words: *wholesale; marketing principles, wholesale turnover, consumer choice, primary marketing information, inventory, customer satisfaction.*

Introduction

In the context of innovative development of the Uzbek economy, priority is given to processing and deep structural changes in industry, production of competitive products, finding new international markets and increasing exports, use of transit potential, uninterrupted supply of raw materials to industries, balanced regional development. The implementation of these tasks is also related to wholesale trade activities. The development and growth of wholesale trade will strengthen inter-sectoral and inter-sectoral ties and ensure economic growth.

The main purpose of the analysis and planning of wholesale turnover in an innovative economy is to ensure the continuity of production and regular supply of retail goods and improve the quality of customer service. Achieving these goals involves studying the needs of buyers (manufacturers, retailers, end users) based on marketing principles and finding sources to purchase goods to fully meet their needs.

The main part

In the context of an innovative economy, it is important for every wholesale organization and enterprise to analyze and plan its wholesale turnover. The main purpose of wholesale turnover analysis and planning is to create stocks to ensure uninterrupted supply of retail goods and to improve the quality of services provided to customers. In this regard, the planning of wholesale turnover in an innovative economy includes:

study the dynamics of wholesale turnover and supply volumes by major groups of goods;

Measurement and determination of the level of factors influencing the development and growth of wholesale trade turnover;

study the reasons for the growth of costs in the field of barter and shortcomings in trade activities;

development of measures to prevent and eliminate risks (threats) in the planning of wholesale turnover;

Defining the strategy and tactics of marketing activities of the wholesale enterprise.

The marketing analysis of a wholesale enterprise should take into account not only the socio-economic development of the service area, but also the production capacity of suppliers, as well as the planned volume and structure of imports from other regions of the country.

The main tasks of analysis and planning of turnover in wholesale trade are:

assessment and study of the dynamics of the development of wholesale trade across all regions and groups of goods;

Identification and quantification of factors influencing changes in the volume of wholesale sales of products;

Analysis of contracts for the supply of products to retail and catering enterprises;

Identify reserves and opportunities to increase wholesale turnover by region and product group.

The database for the analysis and planning of wholesale turnover is the data of accounting and statistical reports, operational information on the trade and economic situation of the enterprise, associations and unions of the industry, as well as information and analytical materials of government. In the process of analysis of wholesale turnover, enterprises solve a number of problems, which can be divided into two groups: the purchase and sale of goods and services.

Rational use of the regions in the balanced development of the regions is a topical issue, with a correct assessment of the reserves and opportunities for the development of the country's economy. Not all regions have the same opportunities. In one region there are more opportunities for the cultivation of agricultural products, in another - industrial production, in another - their processing, in another - transport infrastructure. The importance of the exchange and optimal distribution of commodity and material resources is growing in the smooth development of the regions. In other words, the role of wholesale trade in the supply of raw materials and other material resources to industrial areas, and from this area to the regions where semi-finished products, components and spare

parts processing enterprises are located, and thus the finished product to the consumer market is invaluable.

The main and primary principle of marketing is to identify the factors influencing the purchasing choice of manufacturing enterprises and retailers, who are the main buyers of wholesalers, and to assess the level of customer satisfaction in the planning of wholesale turnover, taking into account consumer orientation. This is because in the planning of wholesale turnover, secondary information obtained only on the basis of the analysis of the dynamics of wholesale turnover in the previous year is not always sufficient. In a free competitive market, every wholesaler and organization collects, analyzes and makes the necessary decisions based on the needs of its customers.

Therefore, the author notes that among small businesses, entrepreneurs engaged in the retail sale of household appliances (refrigerators, televisions, vacuum cleaners, electric ovens, etc.), computers, furniture, entrepreneurs, some entities engaged in the processing of technical and industrial products an expert survey was conducted. The expert survey examined the level of importance of factors that manufacturers and retailers should pay attention to when choosing their wholesale suppliers, i.e., when purchasing goods. Factors influencing procurement selection were assessed on a 10-point scale (Table 1).

Table 1

Classification of factors influencing the consumer choice of production and retail enterprises in the wholesale procurement and their level of importance

№ Factors influencing consumer choice Significance of indicators (on a 10-point scale)

1.	Product reliability and strength	7,4	
2.	Product safety during operation	7,3	
3.	Payment and initial purchase terms	7,2	
4.	Warranty period and after-sales service	7,1	
5.	Delivery and operating costs	6,9	
6.	The suitability of the product for its function	6,3	
7.	Delivery reliability and stability	6,1	
8.	Product life	5,6	
9.	Supplier market position, reputation and brand popularity		3,9
10.	Product sales methods and sales promotion	3,0	
11.	Transmission of information about new types of products		2,3

In planning the wholesale turnover of wholesalers whose activities comply with the principles of marketing, it is important to consider not only the analysis of the dynamics of wholesale turnover in previous years, but also the factors influencing the consumer choice of their customers. Factors influencing consumer choice ultimately also affect the volume of wholesale turnover.

Conclusion

The study of the activities of wholesale trade organizations and enterprises operating in our country, the analysis and planning of wholesale trade, the identification of problems associated with marketing activities and the development of recommendations for solutions are among the pressing issues. The successful development of each wholesale trade organization and enterprise will ensure the socio-economic development of the region in which it operates, the supply of industry, processing industries and the saturation of the consumer market.

The success of the wholesale business is largely due to customer focus. Customer orientation, in turn, includes:

- accurate identification of customer needs;

- compliance of the developed standards and planned indicators with the identified needs;

- Problems arising in strategic and operational level service processes and their solutions;

- organization of wholesale services for products purchased by the buyer;

- Differentiation of customer services.

In the context of an innovative economy, when planning wholesale turnover on the basis of marketing principles, it is advisable to do the following:

- creation of stocks to prevent and eliminate risks (risks) in the planning of wholesale turnover, determination of the daily supply of stocks and stocks;

- Development of scientifically based forecasting and economic-mathematical models of industrial and consumer goods production and consumer basket norms to assess the development prospects of demand for each commodity group in the planning of wholesale turnover and analyze its balance with the supply of commodity groups.

- Development of perspective strategies for the development of pre-sales and after-sales service to customers in the marketing activities of wholesale enterprises and organizations;

- Implementation of investment projects in areas with high wholesale turnover, the establishment of logistics centers and enterprises for processing and sorting of

products, as well as the construction and modernization of refrigerated storage tanks, central storage warehouses.

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